

When nocturnally migrating birds encounter low-level light pollution patches: a case study from the Croatian coast[☆]

Simon Hirschhofer^{a,b,*}, Peter Ranacher^a, Robert Weibel^a, Barbara Helm^b,
Davor Ćiković^c, Sanja Barišić^c, Louie Taylor^c, Maja Bjelić, Laušić^d, Baptiste Schmid^b

^a University of Zurich, Department of Geography, Zurich, Switzerland

^b Swiss Ornithological Institute, Department of Bird Migration, Sempach, Switzerland

^c Croatian Academy of Sciences and Arts, Institute of Ornithology, Zagreb, Croatia

^d Public Institution Nature Park Vransko Jezero, Biograd na Moru, Croatia

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ABSTRACT

Artificial light is a pollutant of growing global concern. For nocturnally migrating birds, the consequences can be fatal. Attracted and disoriented by illuminated infrastructure, birds can become victims of collisions, especially when visibility is reduced by fog and clouds. Birds crossing large, predominantly dark bodies of water can suddenly be confronted with patches of lit coastal areas. In contrast, when flying over land along the coast, birds are sequentially confronted with lit areas and are likely to rely on different navigation cues. We deployed two ornithological radars in proximity along the Croatian coast: one at a light-polluted site and one at a near-natural site. The aim was to maximise the contrast in light pollution while keeping other site-specific factors similar. We monitored the consecutive spring migration seasons of 2023 and 2024 and modelled the effect of light pollution on the number of birds in the air, mean airspeeds and mean flight altitudes, considering atmospheric, temporal, and directional predictors. Our results are partially hampered by the fact that we had to exclude a second radar pair from the analysis due to a technical defect. Nevertheless, we found evidence for attraction towards light pollution of sea-crossing birds in the remaining radar pair. Furthermore, we found a significant contribution of light pollution to the reduction of mean airspeeds and altitudes, especially in an overcast context. Besides indicating disorientation, our results raise serious concerns about increased numbers of bird collisions associated with migration peaks and impaired visibility, even with lower-intensity light pollution.

1. Introduction

Human activities are known to alter established avian migration patterns across taxa (Bauer and Hoyer, 2014). Nocturnally migrating birds can be severely affected by night-time lighting (Convention on Migratory Species, 2024). As an effect, birds can suffer from confusion due to artificial light at night (ALAN), sometimes to the point where they become severely disoriented, which can ultimately lead to exhaustion, increased risk of predation or fatal collisions (Van Doren et al., 2017; Korner et al., 2022). In addition, birds have been found to be attracted to light-polluted areas when looking for a place to stop, rest and refuel, which might be especially an issue after crossing geographic barriers (Horton et al., 2023).

Here, we consider phototactic effects as attraction to or avoidance of

light pollution, along with behavioural responses likely caused by to confusion and disorientation. Such effects have been documented in migrating birds, affecting migration intensity (Van Doren et al., 2017), flight altitude (Cabrera-Cruz et al., 2019), and airspeed (Van Doren et al., 2017). Studies on how migratory birds respond to light pollution, however, often present a complex and even conflicting picture (Cochran and Graber, 1958; Nemes et al., 2023). While most studies find that birds are attracted to areas with higher levels of light pollution, there is evidence to the contrary, showing that birds sometimes avoid light-polluted areas during flight (Korpach et al., 2022) and as a stopover (Cabrera-Cruz et al., 2020). Attraction and repulsion by light likely depends on context: while high levels of light pollution are found to attract migrating birds on a large scale, they act as a repellent on a local scale (McLaren et al., 2018).

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* Corresponding author at: Winterthurerstrasse 190, 8057 Zürich, Switzerland.

E-mail address: simon.hirschhofer@geo.uzh.ch (S. Hirschhofer).

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The context also includes the intensity of nocturnal illumination. Most studies on avian migrants' responses to light pollution have focused on high-intensity light pollution in large cities. Although findings from environments with relatively low light intensity are rare, they are nevertheless worth considering. This is because, although lower-intensity or bird-friendly lighting still influences migratory behaviour (Cabrera-Cruz et al., 2021), this behavioural change is significantly less pronounced than at higher light intensities (Osterhaus et al., 2025).

Furthermore, visibility plays an important role, too. Low cloud cover (LCC) and fog have been found amplify the response to light pollution (Cabrera-Cruz et al., 2021). Measurements of light intensity in light-polluted environments show that brightness can increase tenfold under thick clouds (Kyba et al., 2011), providing a straightforward explanation for why migrating birds are especially attracted to artificial light under overcast conditions (Rebke et al., 2019; Van Doren et al., 2021; Weisshaupt et al., 2022). Similarly, dense cloud cover exacerbates confusion and disorientation caused by light pollution, further reducing airspeed (Bruderer et al., 1999).

Finally, there are hints that birds are particularly sensitive to light pollution after crossing a larger body of water, and might become victim to collisions with illuminated windows and other infrastructure more often (Van Doren et al., 2021). Although this hypothesis has not been directly studied, the authors of the aforementioned study highlight that it should be investigated further. To our knowledge, this has not yet been done.

Attraction to light pollution poses two major risks for birds. First, artificial light can draw birds to inferior habitats with reduced quality and quantity of potential food sources (Burt et al., 2023; Morelli et al., 2023). Secondly, night-time lighting increases the risk of collisions with windows and other man-made structures, resulting in significant annual losses which are likely to affect population dynamics (Van Doren et al., 2021). These collisions result in significant losses each year and are likely to affect population dynamics (Erickson et al., 2005).

We selected our study area to include birds with different migration directions, which likely rely on different navigation cues. In coastal regions, migration is often bimodal: some birds cross the sea, while others follow the coastline (Bruderer and Liechti, 1998; Weisshaupt et al.,

2018). We here refer to them as sea-crossing and coastal migrants, respectively. Given that the sea is relatively dark, sea-crossing migrants are likely attracted to light from afar, potentially increasing migration intensity at light-polluted coastal sites compared to dark, near-natural sites. In contrast, coastal migrants likely use the coastline as a navigational landmark and may be less affected by artificial light, resulting in similar migration intensities at light-polluted and near-natural locations (Koistinen, 2000; Weisshaupt et al., 2022). Nevertheless, coastal migrants may still experience confusion and disorientation when passing light-polluted areas. Our study design allows us to differentiate between responses in migration intensity and changes in flight speed and altitude for both migration directions.

A preceding study observed such bimodal directionality along the Croatian coast (Hirschhofer et al., 2025). Here, one group of migrants was crossing the Adriatic Sea from the Italian coast towards Croatia on a roughly SSW to NNE axis. The other group followed the coastline along an SE to NW axis (Fig. 1). Furthermore, light pollution is patchy along the Croatian coastline (Elvidge et al., 2021), presenting opportunities for a suitable study setup.

To analyse bird migration patterns in response to light pollution patterns, two BirdScan ornithological radars were deployed along the Croatian Adriatic coast. The radars were installed 6.7 km apart, in the town of Rovinj and the Palud ornithological reserve, to maximise the contrast between light-polluted and near-natural conditions while keeping other geographic factors similar. The radars recorded nocturnal spring migration from March to May in both 2023 and 2024. BirdScan quantifies bird movement based on individual radar echoes, allowing to separate migratory fluxes by migration direction. We used this capability to study how birds respond to light pollution when migrating over the sea versus along the coast, focusing on migration intensity, mean airspeed, and mean flight altitude. Based on the literature, we formulated the following hypotheses:

Migration intensity of sea-crossing migrants is higher at the light-polluted site than at the dark site, after controlling for atmospheric conditions and seasonality. For coastal migrants, the association between light pollution and migration intensity is weaker or absent. Low cloud cover (LCC) is negatively associated with migration intensity,

Fig. 1. Overview of the study area. The map shows the two radar sites, topography, and light pollution as sky glow (the ratio of artificial to natural sky brightness). For reference, at ratios ≥ 0.5 , the Milky Way is no longer visible. The inset enlarges the Rovinj area to provide a clearer view of night-time illumination around the radar sites. The transparent blue arrow indicates the direction of sea-crossing migration, and the transparent red arrow indicates the direction of coastal migration. (For interpretation of the references to colour in this figure legend, the reader is referred to the web version of this article.)

while also modifying the relationship between light pollution and migration intensity, such the effect of light pollution is stronger on nights with higher LCC.

Mean airspeed is lower at the light-polluted site than at the dark site for both sea-crossing and coastal migrants, with a stronger reduction in sea-crossing birds. High LCC further amplifies this effect, leading to the greatest reduction in airspeed on cloudy nights at the light-polluted site.

Flight altitudes are lower over the light-polluted site than over the dark site. High LCC further reduces flight altitude, with the greatest reduction during cloudy nights at the light-polluted site.

2. Methods

2.1. Study region and radar monitoring

We deployed two BirdScan MR1 ornithological radars along the Croatian coast on the Istrian peninsula (Fig. 1). One radar was placed in the city of Rovinj (45° 4' 57.5034" N, 13° 38' 13.524" E; 17 m asl), and the second was placed in the Palud ornithological reserve (45° 2' 22.92" N, 13° 41' 50.928" E; 17 m asl). Two additional radars were deployed in Dalmatia, in Zadar and at Vransko Lake, but technical issues prevented us from including their data (Hirschhofer et al., 2025; S.H. and B.S., personal observation). The two sites differed in light pollution levels, quantified as upward radiance within a 1000-m raster cell neighbourhood using the monthly cloud-free day-night band composite from VIIRS (Elvidge et al., 2021) for March, April, and May in 2023 and 2024 (Rovinj: $20.6 \pm 17.4 \text{ nW}\cdot\text{cm}^{-2}\cdot\text{sr}^{-1}$; Palud: $0.7 \pm 0.5 \text{ nW}\cdot\text{cm}^{-2}\cdot\text{sr}^{-1}$; see Supp. Fig. 1 in the Supporting Information). The distance between the sites was 6.7 km. The distance from the coast to the radar sites was 450 m in Rovinj, 540 m in Palud.

The BirdScan MR1 is a modified marine X-band radar with a pulse length of 70 ns, a wavelength of 3.2 cm, a range resolution of 10 m, and a minimum detection range of 40 m. It detects echoes from individual small passerine birds up to 1000 m above ground level (m agl). The radar rotates at 0.8 Hz around a 0.2° nutated axis, which enables the calculation of the birds' ground speed and direction. As an object passes through the radar beam, it is repeatedly illuminated. Birds are distinguished from other echoes and classified into broad groups based on echo intensity and observed changes in echo intensity over time, which correspond to the size of the bird and specific wing-flapping patterns. We focus here on two groups of small to medium-sized birds: continuously flapping birds (e.g. waders) and intermittently flapping birds (e.g. passerines), both with a flapping frequency of 25 Hz or less (Bruderer et al., 2010). The filtering and frequency threshold help to reduce contamination from non-bird echoes and non-migratory movements by excluding e.g. larger, local birds or insects. To estimate the number of birds, echoes were corrected for detection probability (Schmaljohann et al., 2008; Schmid et al., 2019). Birds are not equally detectable at different altitudes due to two main factors. First, at higher altitudes, as the bird's distance from the radar increases, the received signal weakens, reducing the probability of detecting smaller birds. Second, due to the shape of the radar beam, the projected area covered is smaller near the radar and larger farther away. To account for the second sampling bias, we applied a correction factor to calculate the hourly migration traffic rate (MTR), the number of birds passing within 500 m of the radar per hour. For further analysis, we used the R package *suncalc* (Thieurmél and Elmarhraoui, 2022) to calculate site-specific times of civil dusk and dawn (the moment when the centre of the sun is 6° below the horizon), and defined the time between as nighttime. We then averaged the MTR to reflect the mean migration intensity of radar nights.

We monitored the nocturnal spring migration from 1 March to 31 May in 2023 and 2024. Several radar nights were excluded from analysis due to technical problems, and rain contamination, which may cause false positives. Of the total 368 radar nights, we retained 370 for the analysis.

In total, 456,827 bird echoes were recorded at the two radar sites between March and May in 2023 and 2024. Filtering for passerine- and wader-type echoes resulted in 222,747 remaining echoes for analysis, of which 160,865 contained directional information. Removed echoes were either recorded during the day, belonged to other bird classes (e.g., larger birds or swift-type birds), or had classifications with high uncertainty.

2.2. Distinguishing between sea-crossing and coastal migration

To quantify sea-crossing and coastal migration separately, we first defined the coastline by manually approximating a line in QGIS and determining its orientation (326°). Bird echoes with flight directions perpendicular to the coastline ($\pm 45^\circ$) were classified as sea-crossing, while those parallel ($\pm 45^\circ$) were classified as coastal. To distinguish between sea-crossing and coastal migration, we then calculated the proportion of sea-crossing and coastal echoes relative to the total number of included bird echoes per radar night. This proportion was then used to recalculate the MTR for both directions.

2.3. Atmospheric data

To calculate the airspeed of birds and account for atmospheric effects in the modelling, we used hourly ERA5 reanalysis data (Hersbach et al., 2020) at single-altitude levels (LCC up to 2000 m above sea level in percentage coverage, air temperature at 2 m above ground, and air pressure at sea level), and pressure-level intervals of 25 hPa with a grid size of 0.25° (u- and v-wind components, representing west to east and south to north wind).

From the downloaded atmospheric variables, we extracted exact grid cell values for the two radar sites. LCC, temperature and pressure were provided on single levels, so no further selection was required. The processing of the wind data is described in more detail below.

To merge wind data with bird echoes, we converted echo altitudes to corresponding pressure levels using the barometric formula. We then used the wind data to calculate the airspeeds of individual birds from the measured groundspeeds, as airspeeds better reflect the in-flight behaviour of birds (Hedenström and Åkesson, 2017). We matched bird flight altitudes to pressure levels in the wind data and then calculated u- and v-movement vectors for each recorded bird from the measured ground-speed and flight direction. Airspeed is then the subtraction of the u- and v-wind vectors from a bird's u- and v-movement vectors. To reconcile the airspeeds with the aggregated MTR data, the resulting airspeed was averaged over complete radar nights, weighting each echo with the correction factor that accounts for the probability of detection.

Second, to use wind as an environmental predictor in the analysis, we calculated the mean headwind and crosswind for each radar night and separately for sea-crossing and coastal migration. We define headwind as the wind speed parallel to the mean direction of flight per night and radar site and separately for sea-crossing and coastal migration, with negative values indicating winds in the mean direction of migration and positive values indicating winds against the mean direction of migration, and crosswind as the wind perpendicular to the mean direction of flight, without distinguishing between winds from the right or left. We thereafter selected the pressure level with the highest bird activity for each radar night and migration direction and calculated the headwind and crosswind relative to the mean flight directions determined from the echo data, again weighted with the correction factor for the probability of detection.

2.4. Light pollution data

Following the study design, which included two regions, each containing one light-polluted and one near-natural site, we modelled light pollution as a categorical variable with the factors light-polluted and dark. This allowed us to better account for the light pollution contrasts

within regions rather than absolute brightness.

Initially, we included light pollution as a continuous variable, derived from the monthly (March to May) cloud-free averaged upward radiance of night lights from the NASA/NOAA Visible Infrared Imaging Radiometer Suite (VIIRS) day/night band low-light imaging data at 15 arcsec raster resolution (Elvidge et al., 2021). The problem with absolute measurements of light pollution as a continuous variable was the strong concavity between measured light pollution, the radar locations, and night of the year (NoY) during modelling. This led to highly unstable and unrealistic predictions of the response variables. These problems were eliminated by using light pollution as a categorical variable.

2.5. Modelling intensity and behaviour

To explain the variability in migration traffic rate (MTR), mean airspeed and mean flight altitude, we built 3 Generalised Additive Models (GAMs), one for each of our response variables (MTR, airspeed, and flight altitude) using the *mgcv* package in R (Wood, 2023).

Response variables were modelled using appropriate error distributions: MTR was modelled with a quasi-Poisson family and a log link to account for overdispersion and positive count data, while airspeed and flight altitude were modelled using a Gaussian family with an identity link. All models were fitted using Restricted Maximum Likelihood (REML) to reduce the risk of overfitting.

Our model structure was designed to test the effects of light pollution while accounting for environmental and seasonal drivers. We modelled the non-linear effects of continuous predictors using thin plate regression splines. The full model structure included:

- **Smooth terms:** non-linear effects of air pressure, air temperature, LCC, headwind, and crosswind, with separate smooths for sea-crossing and coastal migration.
- **Seasonal term:** a smooth term for night number of the year (NoY), with a separate smooth for each year to account for inter-annual variation.
- **Light pollution:** a parametric term for light pollution (categorical: light-polluted/dark) and its interaction with LCC and migration direction.
- **Temporal autocorrelation:** to account temporal autocorrelation in the time-series data, we incorporated a first-order autoregressive correlation structure (corAR1), nested within each unique combination of year and migration direction.

We assessed multicollinearity among predictors by checking for concavity, the non-linear analogue to collinearity in GAMs. After model fitting, we quantified the contribution of each predictor by calculating its percentage of explained deviance using the *gam.hp* R package (Lai et al., 2024). We visualised the marginal effect of each predictor, by generating model predictions using the *ggeffects* R package (Lüdtke, 2018), holding all other covariates constant at their mean or reference values.

To quantify the effects of light pollution on migration intensity, airspeed, and flight altitude, we performed a post-hoc analysis. We calculated estimated marginal means (EMMs) for the two levels of light pollution and the two migration directions using the *emmeans* R package (Lenth, 2017). We then performed pairwise contrasts between these EMMs to quantify their differences, including standard errors, and a *p*-values, directly testing the significance of light pollution effects while accounting for other covariates.

3. Results

Here, we focus on the reporting of the modelled effects of light pollution and LCC on bird migration for the two radar sites at Rovinj and Palud. The Supporting Information details migration phenology, airspeeds, and flight altitudes (Supp. Figs. 2 to 7), as well as the effects of

atmospheric and temporal predictors (Supp. Figs. 8 to 10).

3.1. Effect of light pollution on mean nightly migration intensity (MTR)

The Mean nightly migration intensity for the light-polluted and dark site was 187 birds·h⁻¹·km⁻¹ for sea-crossing migration ($Q_1 = 55$, $Q_3 = 234$), and 123 birds·h⁻¹·km⁻¹ for coastal migration ($Q_1 = 60$, $Q_3 = 158$). There were nights with little or no activity, as well as extreme nights with mean MTRs of 1526 birds·h⁻¹·km⁻¹ for sea-crossing and 778 birds·h⁻¹·km⁻¹ for coastal migration. The GAM explained 66.5 % of the total deviance in mean nightly MTR (adjusted $R^2 = 0.65$).

The model estimated a 22.9 % increase in the MTR from the dark to the light-polluted site for sea-crossing migration, although this difference was not statistically significant (95 % CI: -2.5 % to +55.0 %; $p = 0.157$). For coastal migration, the estimated increase was 4.6 % from the dark to the light-polluted site, but this difference was also not statistically significant (95 % CI: -8.3 % to +19.6 %; $p = 0.560$) (Fig. 2).

LCC generally had a negative effect on MTR. The effect was significant for sea-crossing migration for both light-polluted and dark sites ($p < 0.001$ at the dark site and $p = 0.002$ at the light-polluted site), but not significant for coastal migration ($p = 0.419$ at the dark site and $p = 0.110$ at the light-polluted site). The interaction between LCC, migration direction, and light pollution explained 10.8 % of the total deviance.

3.2. Effect of light pollution on mean nightly airspeed

The mean nightly airspeed for both sites was 11.2 m·s⁻¹ for sea-crossing migration ($Q_1 = 9.7$ m·s⁻¹, $Q_3 = 12.6$ m·s⁻¹), and 9.6 m·s⁻¹ for coastal migration ($Q_1 = 8.4$ m·s⁻¹, $Q_3 = 10.4$ m·s⁻¹). The GAM explained 77.8 % of the total deviance in mean nightly airspeed (adjusted $R^2 = 0.757$).

The model predicted significantly lower mean airspeeds at the light-polluted site than at the dark site for both sea-crossing and coastal migration, with a stronger effect for sea-crossing migration. Airspeeds were 0.94 m·s⁻¹ lower (95 % CI: 0.55 to 1.33 m·s⁻¹; $p < 0.001$) at the light-polluted site than at the dark site for sea-crossing migration, and 0.55 m·s⁻¹ lower (95 % CI: 0.24 to 0.86 m·s⁻¹; $p < 0.001$) for coastal migration. Light pollution accounted for 7 % of the model's total deviance (Fig. 3).

LCC had no significant effect on mean airspeeds.

3.3. Effect of light pollution on mean nightly flight altitude

The mean nightly flight altitude for both sites was 393 m ASL for sea-crossing migration ($Q_1 = 338$ m, $Q_3 = 447$ m), and 359 m for coastal migration ($Q_1 = 317$ m, $Q_3 = 405$ m). The GAM explained 58.2 % of the total deviance in mean nightly flight altitude (adjusted $R^2 = 0.549$).

The model predicted significantly lower mean flight altitude at the light-polluted site than at the dark site for both sea-crossing and coastal migration, again with a stronger effect for sea-crossing migration. Mean flight altitude was 52.2 m lower (95 % CI: 40.44 to 63.96 m; $p < 0.001$) at the light-polluted site than at the dark site for sea-crossing migration, and 44.7 m lower (95 % CI: 27.26 to 62.14 m; $p < 0.001$) for coastal migration. Light pollution accounted for 16 % of the model's total deviance (Fig. 4).

LCC had a significant effect on flight altitudes at the light-polluted site. For coastal migration, an additional decrease of 43 m was estimated ($p < 0.008$) when the sky was fully covered, while the reduction was 58 m ($p < 0.029$) for sea-crossing migration. The interactive effect between LCC, migration direction, and light pollution explained 6.8 % of the model's total deviance.

4. Discussion

We tested the responses of nocturnally migrating birds to light pollution in terms of migration intensity (MTR), mean airspeed and

Fig. 2. Effects of light pollution on migration intensity (MTR) during the spring migration seasons of 2023 and 2024 in Istria. Marginal effects of light pollution, and LCC in interaction with light pollution, for sea-crossing and coastal migration intensities. The panels show the mean estimate and 95 % prediction intervals.

Fig. 3. Effects of light pollution on mean airspeed during the spring migration seasons of 2023 and 2024 in Istria. Marginal effects of light pollution, and LCC in interaction with light pollution, for mean nightly airspeeds of sea-crossing and coastal migration. The panels show the mean estimate and 95 % prediction intervals.

Fig. 4. Effects of light pollution on mean flight altitude during the spring migration seasons of 2023 and 2024 in Istria. Marginal effects of light pollution, and LCC in interaction with light pollution, for mean nightly flight altitude for sea-crossing and coastal migration. The panels show the mean estimate and 95 % prediction intervals.

mean flight altitude. Together, these variables form a measurable proxy for a phototactic response (Van Doren et al., 2017) and provide insight into light-pollution-induced disorientation (Bruderer et al., 1999). Here, we present the first full-season, individual-based quantification of these responses.

4.1. The effect of light pollution on migration intensity (MTR) and flight behaviour

Our results suggest that birds respond to light pollution, even at relatively low intensities (20.6 nW·cm⁻²·sr⁻¹ in Rovinj). Although the increase in the estimated MTR at the light-polluted site compared to the dark site was not statistically significant, the trend towards higher MTR,

together with the clearly reduced airspeeds and flight altitudes, suggests that birds exhibit an in-flight behavioural response to light pollution, particularly after crossing the sea. This response appears to occur even under comparatively low levels of light pollution.

Although the two radar sites were separated by less than 7 km, our models indicated notable behavioural differences between the light-polluted site and the dark site that could not be attributed to atmospheric or seasonal effects. Most birds migrate across the Mediterranean and the Adriatic Sea on a broad front (Trösch et al., 2005; Gargallo et al., 2011). Although topography can divert broad front migration (Aurbach et al., 2018), the area surrounding the two radars is relatively flat. Therefore, we expect that migration across the Adriatic Sea in this region is largely unimpeded, with minimal differences over the short distance separating the two radars.

The wide confidence intervals around the estimated differences in migration intensity likely reflect the substantial natural variability in MTR between nights rather than model uncertainty alone. The MTR exhibited a wide interquartile range (55 to 234 birds·h⁻¹·km⁻¹ for sea-crossing and 60 to 158 for coastal migration) and nights with little or no detectable migration were frequent. Such variability, including sporadic peaks of very high MTR, increases the overall variance of the data and could consequently have broadened the confidence intervals in the model. Although the GAM accounted for seasonal variation in the MTR, a considerable proportion of the variability remained unexplained, as indicated by the moderate adjusted R² of 0.65. This suggests that other site-specific differences in bird passage that were not captured by the GAM contributed substantially to the residual variation. Despite this uncertainty, the estimated 22 % higher MTR at the light-polluted site for sea-crossing migration suggests that light pollution may influence the spatial distribution of migrants as they approach the shoreline. In contrast, the MTR for coastal migration showed only a small, non-significant increase of 4.6 % between the dark and light-polluted sites, suggesting that light pollution may have a comparatively weaker effect when birds rely on topographic cues for navigation. This pattern is consistent with the idea that light attraction depends on birds' reliance on navigational cues: coastal migrants are likely to follow the shoreline regardless of light (Koistinen, 2000; Weisshaupt et al., 2022). While the observed difference between sea-crossing and coastal MTR is not statistically significant, it highlights the need for further investigations across additional sites and migratory contexts to clarify whether this pattern is more general.

In contrast, measured airspeeds and flight altitudes exhibited narrower distributions, indicating greater consistency of these response variables between nights. In the case of airspeeds, the GAM also captured a higher proportion of the overall variability in the measurements. Thus, the models estimated significantly lower airspeeds and, more concerning, reduced flight altitudes for both migration directions when birds were over light-polluted areas. These results suggest that, although the MTR fluctuates markedly, leading to clear yet insignificant trends, the behavioural in-flight adjustments of migrating birds over illuminated areas represent a consistent response to light pollution.

Our findings regarding flight altitude however contrasts with previous findings, in which migrating birds increased their flight altitudes in response to light pollution (Cabrera-Cruz et al., 2019). However, that study suggested that the observed altitude increase may have been a response to urban heat rather than light pollution per se. To our knowledge, the altitudinal response of migrating birds to light pollution remains poorly understood and warrants further investigation.

Further research is needed to determine whether this altitudinal response has a detrimental effect on migrating birds. There is conflicting evidence, which makes it difficult to reach a conclusion. While some studies have found that birds follow light sources as a guiding aid (Weisshaupt et al., 2022), it has been assumed that the collision rate of nocturnally migrating birds increases after the crossing of aquatic barriers, particularly when visibility is reduced (Van Doren et al., 2021). Although our results too suggest such a hypothesis, the model failed to

provide statistically significant support for it. Ultimately, light attraction may be problematic, regardless of whether it is initially used as an orientation cue. When seeking a suitable stopover site after crossing a barrier, migrating birds that were previously drawn to light-polluted areas may encounter lower-quality stopover habitats (Horton et al., 2023), or collide with urban infrastructure (Van Doren et al., 2021; Korner et al., 2022). Recent evidence further suggests that even bird-friendly lighting, such as shielded fixtures or lights with higher dominant wavelengths, can still elicit in-flight behavioural alterations (Osterhaus et al., 2025). While such lighting strategies reduce the overall impact of artificial light at night, they do not entirely prevent behavioural responses. This indicates that migratory birds remain sensitive to illumination, even under mitigation-oriented designs. The cumulative negative impact of these behavioural reactions is, however, still subject to future research.

In support of the hypothesis that collision risk may be increased, we found reduced airspeeds and lower flight altitudes, which could indicate signs of disorientation in response to light pollution in migrants crossing the sea and those flying along the coast. Our study area does not include tall, illuminated buildings that can be responsible for the deaths of thousands of birds through collisions (Korner et al., 2022). However, there is striking evidence that even a single low building with illuminated windows can result in countless bird collisions (Van Doren et al., 2021). As tourism in Croatia continues to increase (Carić, 2018), likely leading to higher levels of light pollution (Cho et al., 2014), strategies to minimise the risk of bird-building collisions will be increasingly important.

Factors that influence visibility have long been discussed as affecting the navigational abilities of migrating birds and, consequently, interacting with the effects of light pollution (Allen, 1880; Cochran and Graber, 1958). Although birds are capable of maintaining their course even in thick clouds (Griffin, 1972) avoidance behaviour towards clouds and fog during migration has been observed (Panuccio et al., 2019). Our results contribute to this discussion by showing a downward trend in MTR in response to increasing LCC in both light-polluted and dark settings. This effect may reflect the general tendency of birds to avoid migrating under adverse weather conditions involving thick clouds and fog.

Long-term observations have shown that birds accumulate at artificially illuminated structures under overcast conditions (Evans Ogden, 1996; Evans et al., 2007). If this effect were strong in our study area, we might have expected higher MTR at the light-polluted site under high LCC; however, our model did not reveal such a pattern. An explanation could be that the absolute level of artificial illumination in our study site Rovinj was too low to trigger additional accumulation of birds under overcast conditions. No clear interactive effect of light pollution and LCC was observed on migration intensity. However, flight altitudes at the light-polluted site decreased significantly by approximately 16 % for sea-crossing and 12 % for coastal migration under high LCC compared with clear-sky conditions. No such effect occurred at the dark site. This response adds to the main effect of light pollution, which already predicted lower flight altitudes at the light-polluted site regardless of LCC.

4.2. Conservation implications

The reaction of birds to light pollution demonstrated here has implications for the conservation of migratory birds. Our results suggest that migrating birds exhibit an in-flight response to artificial night-time lighting, even at low levels of illumination. This finding is consistent with previous research (Cabrera-Cruz et al., 2021; Osterhaus et al., 2025). Croatia is considered one of the most progressive countries in terms of light pollution regulation. Since 2008, the government has been working on measures to define, record, limit and prevent light pollution (Widmer et al., 2022). To this end, the first laws to prevent light pollution were introduced in 2019 (Hrvatski Sabor, 2019), followed by legislation establishing lighting zones with strict limits (Ministarstvo

zaštite okoliša i energetike, 2020), including zones where only natural light is permitted. Nevertheless, local ecologists still view light pollution as a threat (Ječmenica et al., 2020). With increasing tourism in the region, the anthropogenic influence on the Croatian coastal nightscape may grow further in the near future (Cho et al., 2014; Carić, 2018). Especially in coastal regions, we must be aware that night-time lighting could have far-reaching consequences.

Light-induced bird building collisions are believed to be one of the top contributors to avian mortality during migration. Estimates speak of up to a billion birds that are annually killed by collisions in the US alone (Loss et al., 2015). The problem of light pollution has been recognised publicly, and first actions of collision mitigation are being implemented in several locations of the world (Evans Ogden, 2002; Loss et al., 2023). Promising are large-scale actions such as the lights out initiative in Texas, USA (Saha, 2017; Convention on Migratory Species, 2024; Farnsworth et al., 2024), and the Bird Friendly Building Program (Evans Ogden, 2002).

Because bird migration is a highly dynamic phenomenon, it has been suggested that conservation measures can be so too (Horton et al., 2021). Temporarily switching off non-essential illumination at nights where intense migration is expected can offer most birds safe passage. This however requires the implementation of accurate forecasting models on a large geographic scale (Kranstauber et al., 2022). In the US, the free availability of continent-wide weather radar data has enabled scientists to implement such a model (Van Doren and Horton, 2018). However, in Europe, the restricted and heterogenous availability of such data has prevented this so far (Desmet et al., 2025). To implement this in the future, nations must work together to synchronise and distribute the data of their operative radar systems. Until then, it would be best to accompany infrastructural projects with an ornithological assessment, especially at potentially sensitive locations, where a lot of migrating birds might accumulate, and where the geographic and anthropogenic environment potentially create fatal situations (Kirby et al., 2008). Adapting lighting schedules of buildings to migrating birds, especially during peak migration nights, could prevent millions of collisions annually.

5. Conclusion

Migratory birds responded differently to light pollution along the Croatian coast, depending on the direction of migration (sea-crossing or along the coast). We detected a significant response in the form of reduced airspeeds and markedly lower flight altitudes at the light-polluted site compared with the near-natural site. This is of concern because lower flight altitudes increase the risk of collisions with illuminated structures, particularly under conditions of reduced visibility. Our results warrant further research that includes more sites and potentially includes a lights-out program as an experimental evaluation. A deeper understanding of how birds are affected by night-time lighting is still urgently needed to understand how we can prevent unnecessary losses during migration. As this is a global phenomenon occurring across diverse geographical and anthropogenic contexts, such research could yield valuable insights.

CRedit authorship contribution statement

Simon Hirschhofer: Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Visualization, Validation, Software, Project administration, Methodology, Investigation, Formal analysis, Data curation, Conceptualization. **Peter Ranacher:** Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Supervision, Methodology, Conceptualization. **Robert Weibel:** Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Supervision, Funding acquisition, Conceptualization. **Barbara Helm:** Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Supervision, Resources, Project administration, Funding acquisition, Conceptualization. **Davor Ćiković:** Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft. **Sanja**

Barisić: Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft. **Louie Taylor:** Project administration. **Maja Bjelić, Laušić:** Project administration. **Baptiste Schmid:** Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Validation, Supervision, Software, Resources, Project administration, Methodology, Investigation, Funding acquisition, Data curation, Conceptualization.

Ethics and consent to participate

Installation and operation of radar permitted by the Croatian ministry of health (permit reference number: 534-03-3-2/2-23-02).

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Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare that they have no competing interests.

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Appendix A. Supplementary data

Supplementary data to this article can be found online at <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.biocon.2025.111620>.

Data availability

The data and the R scripts underlying this research are available at <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17598350>.

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